

The Effect of Giving Boiled Water of Betel Leaves (*Piper beetle* L.) and Red Guava Leaves (*Psidium guajava* L.) through drinking water on abdominal fat in broilers

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Abstract

Broiler (*Gallus domesticus*) is a type of poultry that is widely raised in various communities in Indonesia. However, broilers have weaknesses such as low adaptability and susceptibility to infections, which necessitate an intensive management system. The focus of this study is to identify the ideal mixing ratio between the red guava and betel leaves and to evaluate the effect of combining them on the reduction of the distribution of abdominal fat in broilers. In Banjar Suda, Nyitdah Village, Kediri District, Tabanan Regency, the research carried out over an amount of 35 days using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) involving four treatments and seven replications. Three broilers were included in each replication. P0 was the control group (no extra boiling leaves were added), P1 was the 1:1 ratio of betel and red guava leaves, P2 was the 2:1 ratio, and P3 was the 1:2 ratio. All treatments were given in drinking water at a rate of 5% of weekly body weight. The observed variables include carcass weight, fat pad, mesenteric, ventricular, and abdominal fat. The results of this research demonstrated that, overall variables, there were no significant differences between the treatment and control groups. In contrast to the previous treatments, treatment P3 (1:2) demonstrated a propensity to reduce fat in all categories. The administration of heated water produced from red guava and betel leaves in different ratios (1:1, 2:1, and 1:2) up to 5% of weekly body weight can be concluded to.

Keywords: Abdominal Fat; Broiler; Betel Leaves; Drinking Water; Red Guava Leaves

1. Introduction

Broiler (*Gallus domesticus*) is a type of poultry that is widely raised in various segments of Indonesian society. Population growth and public knowledge of the value of consuming animal protein contribute to the demand for grilled chicken meat.

However, broilers have physiological weaknesses such as low immunity and are prone to diseases, thus requiring an intensive husbandry system. One effort to improve production efficiency and the immunity of broilers is by adding feed additives such as antibiotic growth promoters (AGP). However, the long-term use of AGP can leave residues in animal products (meat, eggs, milk), which pose risks to human health. Therefore, there is a need for safe, effective, and environmentally friendly natural feed additive alternatives

Betel leaves contain phenolic compounds like betel leaves that dominate, which is as much as 1.4-2% [2; 4]. According to [6], Essential oils can stimulate pancreatic juice containing amylase, lipase and protease enzymes to improve the digestion process of feed ingredients that also affect meat production in chickens.

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Guava leaves are mostly composed of flavonoids (>1.4%) and tannins, which are polyphenol chemicals [3]. Because flavonoid ' molecules have antibacterial properties, they can prevent harmful bacteria from growing in the digestive tract, which ultimately improves the body's ability to absorb and use nutrients [1].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Material

The research was conducted out over the course of 35 days, from July 19 to August 23, 2024. There were 84 broilers (un-sexing) in all, housed in an 85 cm x 95 cm wooden cage with three broilers, a feeder, and a drinking waterer. The cage's floor was covered with newspaper after being covered with lime and rice husks. The commercial ration, coded G-10 (for infants aged 1–20 days) and G-11 (for infants aged 21–35 days), was provided ad libitum and was made by PT. Jaffa Comfeed Indonesia Tbk. Table 1 shows the ration's nutritions composition.

Table 1 Nutrient content of broiler rations coded G-10 and G-11

Nutritional content ¹⁾	Ration Type			
	G-10	SNI Standards ²⁾ (8173-2:2022)	G-11	SNI Standards ²⁾ (8173-3:2022)
Water Content (%)	12.0%	13.0%	14.0%	12.0%
Crude Protein/CP (%)	22.0%	20.0%	19.0%	20.5%
Extract Ether/EE (%)	5.0%	4.0%	5.0%	5.0%
Crude Fiber/SK (%)	4.0%	5.0%	6.0%	5.0%
Ash %	7.0%	9.0%	8.0%	7.0%
Calcium (Ca) (%)	0.8-1.10%	0.7-1.2%	0.8-1.1%	0.8-1.10%
Phosphors (P) (%)	0.50%	0.5%	0.45%	0.50%
Aflatoxin (µg/kg)	40 µg/Kg	50 µg/Kg	50 µg/Kg	50 µg/Kg

Information: ¹⁾Broiler feed brochure PT. Jaffa Comfeed Indonesia Tbk; ²⁾Nutrient standards according to Indonesian National Standard (Indonesian: Standard Nasional Indonesia/SNI)

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Experimental design and randomization

This research employed a completely randomized design (CRD) with seven replications, each involving three broilers and four treatments. The four treatments were: P0 (0% betel leaves and red guava leaves), P1 (5% mixture of boiled water of betel leaves and guava leaves from weekly body weight with a ratio of 1:1), P2 (5% mixture of boiled water of betel leaves and guava leaves from weekly body weight with a ratio of 2:1), P3 (5% mixture of boiled water of betel leaves and guava leaves from weekly body weight with a ratio of 1:2).

To determine the average weight and standard deviation, 100 chickens were weighed as part of the chicken randomization process. The DOC used for this investigation was one that weighed between 42.06 ± 2.103 g on average.

2.2.2. Observed Variables

The variables observed in this study were

- Cut weight (g) = The slaughtered broiler weights were taken from a sample of broilers with body weights close to the mean for each treatment unit.
- Percentage of pad fat = The percentage of fat attached to the abdominal cavity of broilers is based on the broiler slaughter/cut weight.
- Percentage of mesenteric fat = Percentage of fat weight attached to the intestine based on broiler slaughter/cut weight

- Percentage ventricular fat = Percentage of fat weight attached to the ventricle based on broiler slaughter weight
 - Abdominal fat percentage = The percentage of total abdominal fat weight, consisting of pad fat, mesenteric fat, and ventricle fat, was calculated based on broiler slaughter weight.
- $$= \frac{\text{pad fat} + \text{mesenteric fat} + \text{ventricular fat}}{\text{Cut weight}}$$

2.3. Data analysis

The analysis of variance was used to examine the data from this study, and Duncan's multiple range test was used to continue the computation if there was a significant difference between the treatments ($P < 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

Results of research on the effects of therapy on abdominal fat in 35-day-old broilers that were fed water supplemented with red guava and boiling betel leaves at a rate of 5% of weekly body weight are shown in Table 2. The ratios of red guava leaf to betel were 1:1 (P1), 2:1 (P2), and 1:2 (P3).

Table 2 The effect of boiled betel leaf and red guava leaf decoction on slaughter/cut weight, percentage of pad fat, mesenteric fat, ventricular fat, and abdominal fat in 35-day-old broiler chickens

Variable	Treatments ¹⁾				SEM ²⁾
	P0	P1	P2	P3	
Cut Weight (g)	2235.71 ^{a3)}	2307.86 ^a	2303.86 ^a	2365.00 ^a	53.06
Pad Fat (%)	0.84 ^a	0.81 ^a	0.80 ^a	0.79 ^a	0.02
Mesenteric Fat (%)	0.23 ^a	0.22 ^a	0.20 ^a	0.20 ^a	0.01
Ventricular Fat (%)	0.31 ^a	0.30 ^a	0.29 ^a	0.28 ^a	0.01
Abdominal Fat (%)	1.36 ^a	1.28 ^a	1.26 ^a	1.23 ^a	0.04

Notes: ¹⁾ Treatments; P0: 0% betel leaf and guava leaf; P1: 5% mixture of boiled water of betel leaf and guava leaf from weekly body weight with a ratio of 1:1; P2: 5% mixture of boiled water of betel leaf and guava leaf from weekly body weight with a ratio of 2:1; P3: 5% mixture of boiled water of betel leaf and guava leaf from weekly body weight with a ratio of 1:2; ²⁾ Standard Error of the Treatment Means; ³⁾ Values with the same letter in the same row indicate no significant difference ($P > 0.05$).

The research results show that the administration of boiled water from betel leaves and red guava leaves at a rate of 5% of weekly body weight with a ratio of 1:1 (P1), 2:1 (P2), and 1:2 (P3) had no significant effect ($P > 0.05$) on reducing abdominal fat in broilers. This is due to the maintenance conditions, temperature, body weight, genetics, and the uniform provision of commercial feed that meets the nutritional needs of broilers. According to [7], feed consumption is influenced by metabolizable energy, temperature, body weight, and crude fiber. [8] Additionally, found no discernible impact on feed consumption from a betel leaf and guava solution up to 25 ml/l. In the digestive system, active substances such as tannins, flavonoids, eugenol, and quercetin function as antioxidants and antimicrobials without having a direct impact on live weight. In line with [3], the supplementation of betel leaf extract did not have a significant impact on the final weight of the chickens. Other factors such as stress and physiological adaptation to phytochemical compounds can also reduce growth impacts. Thus, although there is a descriptive increase in the weight of the cut, the treatment does not provide a statistically significant effect and plays a greater role in maintaining digestive health.

The quantity of pad fat in broilers is not significantly affected by the administration of boiling water containing red guava and betel leaves, according to the research's results ($P > 0.05$). Statistically, the changes were not significant even though the treatments P1, P2, and P3 showed a decrease. Pad fat serves as an energy reserve and is formed due to excess energy intake. Active compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, and eugenol in betel leaves and guava may have the potential to influence fat metabolism—flavonoids increase metabolic efficiency, while tannins can inhibit lipase enzymes. However, these effects have not been strong enough to show significant differences, in line with [10] who stated that the influence of phytochemical compounds depends on the dose, duration of administration, and nutrient interactions. Therefore, the trend of decreased subcutaneous fat is not statistically significant under the conditions of this research.

The amount of mesenteric fat in broilers was not significantly affected by the administration of heated water made from red guava and betel leaves, according to the study's results ($P>0.05$). Mesenteric fat functions as an energy reserve and protects internal organs, and is formed due to excess energy intake. Active compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, and eugenol in guava leaves and betel leaves have the potential to affect fat metabolism. Flavonoids enhance the activity of hormone-sensitive lipase enzymes, and eugenol can increase basal metabolism. However, in this study, the effect was not significant enough to reduce mesenteric fat accumulation noticeably.

In comparison to the control (P0), the percentage of broiler ventral fat is reduced by 3.85% to 7.69% when heated water made from betel and red guava leaves is administered, according to the research's results. P3 had the lowest value (0.48%), while P0 had the highest (0.52%). The difference was not statistically significant ($P>0.05$), despite an overall decrease. Ventricular fat serves as an energy reserve, and its accumulation is influenced by the balance of energy intake and needs. Bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, eugenol, and tannins are suspected to enhance the utilization of fat as energy. stated that flavonoids can increase lipase enzyme activity, while [4] reported that herbal extracts can reduce fat deposition. However, in this study, the reduction in ventricular fat was not statistically significant.

The percentage of abdominal fat in broilers is reduced when heated water contains betel and red guava leaves, according to the study's results, however the difference is not statistically significant ($P>0.05$). Abdominal fat reflects the efficiency of fat metabolism, which is influenced by the balance between energy intake and energy needs. Bioactive compounds such as eugenol, flavonoids, and tannins in betel leaves, as well as polyphenols in red guava leaves, are suspected to play a role in reducing fat accumulation by enhancing metabolism and inhibiting the formation and absorption of fat. [5] reported that betel leaf extract increases basal metabolism and reduces body fat, while [9] stated that flavonoids in red guava leaves can inhibit adipocyte differentiation. In addition, the improvement in digestion efficiency and nutrient absorption due to the enhancement of gut microflora also contributes to directing energy for muscle growth, not fat storage. However, this effect is not strong enough to show a statistically significant difference.

4. Conclusion

The results of the study showed that adding boiled betel leaves and red guava leaves to drinking water in ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 1:2, or 5% of body weight weekly, did not significantly reduce broiler abdominal fat distribution. However, quantitatively, there was a decrease in all abdominal fat components, likely indicating improved nutrient utilization, reducing nutrient inefficiency in broilers, and thus improving livestock health.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are not conflict of interest in this manuscript/paper of publication

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